

CARBON FIBER TOW SPREADING PROCESS USING PNEUMATIC DEVICES AND APPLICATION TO THERMOPLASTIC PREPREG MANUFACTURING

Gyu Hee Lee¹ and Woo Il Lee¹

¹Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Seoul National University
1 Gwanak-ro, Gwanak-gu, Seoul 151-742, Republic of Korea
Email: gyuool@snu.ac.kr, wilee@snu.ac.kr, web page: <http://composite.snu.ac.kr>

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ABSTRACT

Continuous 12k carbon fiber tow spreading process using air knife was investigated. The tow spread width and spread uniformity for 2 different process parameters were quantitatively evaluated. Firstly the discharged air jet flow velocity spatial distribution from air knife nozzle exit with varying flow rates were measured. The turbulent plane jet model fits well with this velocity distribution and it gives the information about the tow sag shape under the jet flow which is affected by the air drag force on the tow surface. The calculated tow tension with varying additional tow length between fixed pins shows a good agreement with experiment. Then carbon fiber tow spreading experiment was conducted for the cases of 6 different air flow rates and 5 additional tow lengths. The spread tow widths for each experimental case were evaluated via image analysis. The concentration of carbon filaments across tow width were also calculated using Beer-Lambert law for assessing the degree of spread filament distribution consistency. The spread tow width asymptotically reaches over 6 times of the original width as the additional tow length increases and the reaching rate is accelerated as the flow rate increases. And the additional tow length around 30 mm gives the best spread uniformity.

1 INTRODUCTION

The composite material whose matrix is thermoplastic polymer has several advantages: short process cycle due to no chemical reaction for curing, higher chemical and impact resistance compared to thermosetting matrix and renewability through remolding process. The viscosity of molten thermoplastic resin, however, is very high compared to thermoset resin which makes it difficult to be infused in fibrous reinforcement. Therefore manufacturing fully impregnated fiber-reinforced thermoplastic product requires long processing time.

The motion of a fluid whose viscosity is η running inside the porous medium is governed by Darcy's Law. In 1-D case the required time t_{imp} to fully impregnate the fiber bed of thickness t with driving resin gauge pressure of P is

$$t_{imp} = \eta t^2 / 2KP \quad (1)$$

K is the permeability coefficient of the medium [1]. For fixed viscosity and driving pressure it is the effective way to diminish the reinforcement thickness t in order to shorten the impregnation time because the impregnation time is proportional to square of the bed thickness. Using spread fiber tow can be one of the solution that satisfies this condition. It not only shortens the resin flow path but also increases the permeability K by widening the average intra-tow filament distance. In addition to that using spread tow plies inside the composite material can inhibit the propagation of microcracks across the plies which can help the composite material get higher fatigue resistance [1-2].

The continuous fiber tow spreading process can be mainly divided into two methods: multi-roll method using convex surface to spread the tow outwardly from center and pneumatic method using air flow through vacuum pump or jet nozzle [1-3]. The multi-roll method can effectively spread tow widely and fast but has instability problem of tow moving path when it slides over the convex surface and filament breakage issue at high line-speed operation. In this study the tow spreading process using highly concentrated air jet flow discharging from air knife over fiber tow surface is covered.

2 EXPERIMENT

The photograph and schematic diagram shown in Figure 1 illustrates the carbon fiber tow spreading system using air knife. The air knife model X-stream™ 10003 (Nex flow) was fixed on the 3-axis stage above the carbon fiber tow. The air knife has the very narrow slit at nozzle exit whose length is 70 mm and the gap width is 0.05 mm. The single line of carbon fiber tow was placed between fixed pins whose diameter is 10 mm and the span length between pins is 100 mm. And the tow was placed in perpendicular direction to x-z plane of the air knife. The untwisted 12k continuous carbon fiber tow unwound from a roving model M807-2 (Mirae Industry) was used whose the initial width w_0 is 6 mm and thickness t is 0.12 mm. The carbon fiber tow was heated in the line heater at temperature of 450 °C for 3~5 minutes before used in the tow spreading experiment.

The air pressure at the air knife entrance was regulated in the range of 0.45~0.5 MPa during whole tow spreading experimental process. The air flow rate Q is controlled by a float-type air flowmeter model RM 23 (Dwyer) which has the controlling range of 5-50 liter/min. The air speed was measured by an impeller-type anemometer model Kestrel-1000 (Kestrel) and the impeller diameter is 25 mm. To perform image analysis of the spread tow camera model 1 V2 (Nikon) was installed and AF-S Micro Nikkor 105 mm 1:2.8G ED lens was mounted. A halogen lamp was also installed to provide enough background light intensity and high contrast image at camera shutter speed of 1/1000.

Figure 1: The experimental fixture for air knife tow spreading system

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Air jet velocity profile emerged from air knife nozzle

The air flow velocity distributions emerge from the air knife nozzle exit for 3 different flow rates ($Q = 30, 40, 50$ liter/min) was measured by anemometer. The air velocity along jet direction, or x-direction measured at air knife center position ($y = 0$) is illustrated in Figure 2. In this figure, the central position velocity increases almost linearly with the air flow rate with the air velocity slowly decaying toward downstream. Figure 3 (a) shows the air velocity contour on the x-y plane measured at $Q = 40$ liter/min. The Reynolds number calculated along the y axis is about 30,000. At this Reynolds number the flow can transit into a fully developed turbulent flow [4].

The average velocity of the turbulent plane jet can be mathematically modeled as the following equation [5].

$$\bar{u} = C(J/\rho x)^{0.5} \operatorname{sech}^2(\sigma(y-y_0)/x) \quad (2)$$

J is a momentum flux across jet ($J = \rho \int u^2 dy$), ρ is a density of air, y_0 is a y-directional deviation from the nozzle exit and finally C and σ are constants. We took $\rho = 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $C = 3.3$, $\sigma = 5.0$, $y_0 = 0.005$ m for fitting experimental velocity measurement results. The dotted line in Figure 2 shows the calculated values of air velocity. The turbulent plane jet data fits the slow decaying tendency of the measured data with error less than 18.9%. Figure 3 (b) is shown the 2-D contour map of the turbulent

plane jet model. At near upstream the velocity achieved from the experiment result is seemed to be more diffusive compared to the analytic model. It might be caused by the low spatial resolution of the impeller-type anemometer. But at the downstream the calculated velocity values shows satisfying estimation of the experimental result.

Figure 2: Air velocity profile along jet direction at $y = 0$

Figure 3: Air velocity 2-D contour map on x-y plane at flow rate $Q = 40$ liter/min.
(a) experimental data (b) turbulent plane jet model

3.2 The tow sag shape and tow tension under plane air jet

The air jet emerging toward the tow surface directly affects tow sag shape and tow tension by inducing air drag force on the surface. The schematic diagram in Figure 4 illustrates the experimental fixture to analyze the relationship between the air velocity and the sag shape of the tow. In this experiment the air flow rate of $Q = 40$ liter/min was remained constant. We introduce a new process variable called “additional tow length” which is the length difference between the sagged tow length l_1

and the initial tow length l_0 . With varying the additional tow length l ($l = 10, 20, 30, 40, 50$ mm) the sagged shape of the tow under the air jet flow was measured and displayed in Figure 5.

Figure 4: The tow sag shape under plane air jet and additional tow length

Figure 5: Experimental data of tow sag shape with varying additional tow length

To find adequate model to describe the sagged shape of the tow the catenary shape model was studied first because it is the simplest model introducing the force balance between the tow tension and its own weight. The catenary curve shape equation is expressed as below [6].

$$x = a(\cosh(y/a) - \cosh(R/a)) \quad (3)$$

$$a = T_0/\mu g$$

μ is the tow weight per unit length, g is the gravitational acceleration, T_0 is the tow tension at the bottom of the sag line, R is a half of the span length between fixed pins. The constant values are $\mu =$

1.188×10^{-3} kg/m for carbon fiber tow used in this study, $g = 9.81$ m/s and $R = 0.050$ m. a value is directly calculated with the additional tow length l by the conservation of length.

$$2a \sinh(R/a) = l_1 = l_0 + l \quad (4)$$

The initial tow length l_0 is the same as $2R$. Tow tension can then be expressed as follows.

$$T = T_0 + \mu gx = \mu g(a \cosh(R/a) + x) \sim \mu g \quad (5)$$

The resultant maximum tension T which is posed at $x = 0$ is nearly zero because μ is quite small for carbon fiber. Calculated catenary line shape for the case of additional tow length $l = 30$ mm is shown with dotted line in Figure 6. As can be seen from the figure, this line is deviated from the measured sag shape data.

We added the air drag force term exerted by the air jet flow to the body force and derived new sag curve model. It can be used under the assumption that the majority of drag force is generated at the concentrated area on the bottom part of the sag shape, where the slope of the line is small ($dx/dy = \tan\theta \ll 1$) so the infinitesimal frontal area affected by the drag force does not change along sag curve line ($dA = w \cos\theta ds \approx w ds$). For fixed x -position at the bottom of the sag curve, the turbulent plane jet velocity of Equation (2) can be expressed as follows

$$\bar{u} = p \operatorname{sech}^2(qy) \quad (6)$$

p and q are constants which vary with the flow rate Q of the air. The example of the velocity profile placed at the bottom of the sag line is illustrated with grey color filled curve in Figure 6. The drag force which is proportional to the square of \bar{u} is added to the body force term. After integrating the governing equation twice, the air-drag induced sag model can be arranged as

$$x = a(\cosh(y/a) - \cosh(R/a)) + (k/3\mu g a)(p/q)^2 [2\{\log(\cosh(qy)) - \log(\cosh(qR))\} - 0.5\{\operatorname{sech}^2(qy) - \operatorname{sech}^2(qR)\}] \quad (7)$$

$$k = (1/2)\rho C_D w$$

C_D is the drag coefficient. $C_D = 0.80$, $w = 0.030$ m values were selected. Unlike in the case of catenary model it is hard to derive length conservation equation in analytic form. Therefore the value of a is obtained by numerical method for each additional tow length cases. The air-drag sag line shape for additional tow length $l = 30$ mm is shown with solid line in figure 6. In this case, $a = 3.60$ m. The solution shape fits much more accurately to the experimental result compared to the catenary model.

Figure 6: Comparison between catenary sag line and air-drag sag line

Maximum tension of the tow for different additional tow length was also calculated using the above air-drag sag model. In this model, the tow tension is expressed as

$$T = \mu g a \sqrt{[\sinh(y/a) + (kp^2/3\mu g a q)(\cosh(2qy) + 2)\tanh(qy)\operatorname{sech}^2(qy)]^2 + 1} \quad (8)$$

To obtain the relationship between the tow tension and additional tow length experimentally, the change of the additional tow length for four different gram-scale weight hanged on the tow was measured. The result graph is shown in Figure 7. In this graph, the tow tension has the unit of gram-force. Both of the experimental and air-drag sag model results show the considerable increment of the tow tension as the additional tow length goes to zero. This phenomenon can be described by a power-law.

$$T = 26.9 l^{-0.54} \quad (T [\text{gf}], l [\text{mm}]) \quad (9)$$

Figure 7: The change of tow tension with varying additional tow length

Above graph shows that under the constant air flow rate the tow tension is determined by the additional tow length. It also shows that the small changes of the tension can cause huge fluctuation of the additional tow length in the large additional tow length region. Therefore, in order to keep the additional tow length constant during continuous tow spreading process, it would be better to use the position sensor with tension controller in order to keep the additional tow length constant. Otherwise the instability of the sag depth which causes the uneven spread quality would occur.

3.3 Tow spread width and spread uniformity measurement under plane air jet

The tow spread widths and spread uniformities along the spread tow width are quantitatively estimated using the image analysis for different air flow rate Q and additional tow length l . According to Beer-Lambert law the brightness value of a grayscale image along the tow width can be the measure of filament concentration in the spread tow. Under the assumption that the tow thickness t does not change considerably across the test section the transmittance of light T and filament concentration c have the following relationship.

$$T = I/I_0 = 10^{-\epsilon c} \quad \text{or} \quad \log_{10} T = -\epsilon c \quad (10)$$

I is the light intensity after passing the absorbent, I_0 is the original light intensity, ϵ is the attenuation coefficient and c is the concentration of the absorbent. We defined the non-dimensionalized filament concentration as

$$c = \partial n / \partial z^* \quad (11)$$

n is the number of filaments in the tow and z^* is non-dimensionalized value of z ($z^* = z/w_0$). It is clear

that the integrated value of c over spread tow width is the overall number of filaments in the tow.

$$n = \int c dz^* = 12,000 \text{ (12k tow)} \quad (12)$$

In order to find the value of attenuation coefficient, the average values of concentration over the spread width $E_w(c)$ and the average values of transmittance over spread width $E_w(T)$ obtained from greyscale brightness values for all experiment cases have been analyzed. In Figure 8 the attenuation coefficient ε is the absolute value of the line slope and was found to be 1.0002×10^{-4} .

Figure 8: Relationship between concentration and transmittance for all experiment cases

Figure 9: Filament concentration profile across z-axis for 3 spread tow cases

By using the attenuation coefficient thus found it becomes possible to estimate the local number of filaments by putting brightness data in Equation (10). The spread width and the spread uniformity along spread tow width were measured with varying flow rates $Q = 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50$ liter/min and additional tow lengths $l = 10, 20, 30, 40, 50$ mm.

Figure 9 shows the example of concentration profile along the tow spread width for 3 different parameter cases (Case A: $Q = 0$ liter/min, $l = 0$ mm, Case B: $Q = 25$ liter/min, $l = 10$ mm, Case C: $Q = 50$ liter/min, $l = 40$ mm). Case A shows the unspread original tow, Case C shows one of the most dispersed appearance and Case B has the intermediate shape between the two cases. Through Case A to C the average value of the filament concentration $E_w(c)$ is lowered considerably. For Case C the average concentration of the filament is nearly 2000 which means that there are about 2000 carbon fiber filaments in a unit z^* ($1 z^* = w_0 = 6$ mm). It is clear that the filament population moves outwardly from the central position as it spreads. It is also possible to discriminate the highly agglomerated region of filaments such as the region near $z^* = 2$ in Case C which is not quite apparent to the naked eye.

Figure 10 shows the normalized width w^* data for different process parameters. In this figure the spread tow width asymptotically reaches about 6.6 times of the original width as the additional tow length increases. The rate of spread width per additional tow length is accelerated as the flow rate increases. The spread width data curve can then be fitted with an exponential form with the length constant λ whose value is almost inversely proportional to the flow rate.

$$w^* = 1 + 5.57\{1 - \exp(-l/\lambda)\} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{where } \lambda = 910.6/Q^{1.2} \quad (l [\text{mm}], Q [\text{liter/min}])$$

Figure 11 illustrates the standard deviation of local filament concentration value along the spread width data which can be used as a spread uniformity criteria for different process parameters. The largest air flow rate ($Q = 50$ liter/min) achieves both large spread width and low deviation of the filament concentration distribution compared to any other flow rates. Additional tow length, however, has the optimal point around 30 mm. In low additional tow length region there are chunks of filaments which are not spread sufficiently and the large gap among them keeps the overall deviation big. On the other hand, in large additional tow length the downstream of the air jet induces the oscillatory movement of the grouped filaments and cannot effectively disperse them.

Figure 10: Normalized tow spread width with varying additional tow length

Figure 11: Filament concentration deviation with varying additional tow length

4 CONCLUSIONS

Manufacturing continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites is difficult due to the high viscosity of molten resin. To reduce the impregnation time of molten thermoplastic resin into unidirectional continuous fiber tow, making the tow thickness small by dispersing the filaments uniformly may be an effective way to facilitate the resin impregnation.

The discharged air jet flow velocity spatial distribution from air knife nozzle exit with varying flow rates were measured. The turbulent plane jet model fits well with this velocity distribution and it gives the information about the tow sag shape under the jet flow which is affected by the air drag force on the tow surface. The air-drag sag model was derived from the catenary model and the calculated tow sag shape and the tow tension based on this model with varying additional tow length between fixed pins show a good agreement with experimental results. Also it is important to observe the additional tow length between fixed pins carefully in large additional tow length operation because the small disturbance of the tension can cause huge fluctuation of the additional tow length or tow sag depth resulting in uneven spread quality.

The carbon fiber tow spreading experiment was conducted for the cases of 6 different air flow rates and 5 additional tow lengths. The concentration of carbon filaments across the spread tow width were estimated via using Beer-Lambert law with measured attenuation coefficient. The spread tow width asymptotically reaches about 6.6 times of the original tow width as the additional tow length increases. The rate of spread width per additional tow length is accelerated as the flow rate increases. The optimal process condition is found to be the flow rate of 50 liter/min and the additional tow length of 30 mm. The optimal process condition in order to obtain the wide tow spread width and small deviation of the filament concentration along spread width is the flow rate of 50 liter/min and additional tow length of 30 mm. In this operating condition the maximum tow tension is estimated around 6.5 gf, the tow spread width is $6.47w_0 = 38.8$ mm and the filament concentration is 309 filaments/mm along the spread width with the standard deviation of 272 filaments/mm.

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